

Visible light photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange in aqueous suspension by using nanocrystalline TiO₂ impregnated with metal-free phthalocyanine pigment

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Abstract : In this paper, the visible light photocatalytic activity of nanocrystalline TiO₂ impregnated with metal-free phthalocyanine pigment (Pc) in aqueous suspension for methyl orange photodegradation has been investigated. For the preparation of the TiO₂ impregnated with phthalocyanine, TiO₂/(Pc), first TiO₂ nanoparticles was prepared by the sol-gel method and calcined at 400 °C. Then nanocrystalline TiO₂/(Pc) was synthesized via the chemical precipitation method and characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS), Fourier transformed infrared (FT-IR) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) techniques. Results revealed that the nanocrystalline TiO₂/(Pc) possesses the anatase structure with the average particle size of about 20–25 nm. The absorption edge of the synthesized TiO₂/(Pc) has been shifted significantly into the visible region. Our results revealed the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/(Pc) increased efficiently than TiO₂ nanoparticles under the visible light. Therefore, synthesized nanocrystalline TiO₂/(Pc) is a suitable photocatalyst for use under visible light which make the applicability of TiO₂ photocatalysts even more versatile.

Keywords : Nanoparticles, TiO₂, phthalocyanine, visible light, methyl orange, photocatalytic activity.

Introduction

Titanium dioxide is widely used as a photocatalyst because it is photochemically stable, non-toxic and cheap. However, the efficiency of using TiO₂ is limited by its relatively large band gap energy (3.2 eV), corresponding to wavelength 370 nm where only 3–5% of solar energy is efficient and by the high recombination rate of electron-hole pairs formed in photocatalytic processes^{1–3}. Some methods have been developed for the enhancement of the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ particles such as increasing its surface to volume ratio, optimization of particle size, coupling of TiO₂ particles with other semiconductor particles, dispersed titanium dioxide species within zeolite cavities, doping metal or nonmetal ions and dye photosensitization of TiO₂^{4–7}.

In the organic dye photosensitization method, the dye absorbed on the TiO₂ surface excited by absorbing visible light and then does the electron injection into the semiconductor conduction band, thus absorption spectra of TiO₂ spread to visible region^{8,9}.

Metal-free phthalocyanine (Pc) has three polymorphic forms (α , β and γ). Two common polymorphic forms are α and β forms¹⁰. Phthalocyanine compounds have received great consideration over the last decade because of their high thermal and chemical stability. Also phthalocyanine compounds show very intense optical absorption in the visible region and act as photosensitizers^{10–15}. Iliev *et al.* reported¹⁶ the degradation of sulfide ions using phthalocyanine complexes absorbed on semiconductor supports such as TiO₂ and Al₂O₃. It was found from

Iliev's study that anchoring the (Pc) complex on TiO_2 forms much more efficient catalyst for the oxidation of sulfide ions compared to the sample obtained by anchoring the (Pc) complex on Al_2O_3 .

To the best of our knowledge¹⁰⁻¹⁶, there has been no other research on the visible light degradation using nanocrystalline undoped TiO_2 impregnated with metal-free phthalocyanine pigment. In this paper, because of the widespread application of methyl orange (Fig. 1) and importance of the removing pollution sources from wastewaters, photocatalytic activity of nanocrystalline TiO_2 impregnated with metal-free phthalocyanine pigment (Pc), TiO_2 /(Pc), for methyl orange photodegradation under visible light has been investigated. Nanocrystalline TiO_2 /(Pc) prepared via the chemical precipitation method and characterized by XRD, DRS, FT-IR and TEM techniques.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of methyl orange.

Experimental

Materials :

Acros organics non-metallic 29H,31H-phthalocyanine complex (Pc) was used without further purification. The tetraisopropylorthotitanate $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_4$, ethanol and methyl orange dye (MO, C.I. 13025) were purchased from Merck.

Synthesis of TiO_2 nanoparticles :

TiO_2 nanoparticles were prepared by the sol-gel method. Tetraisopropylorthotitanate was slowly added to ethanol at the molar ratio of 1 : 6. Then, the mixture was stirred vigorously for 90 min. The final solution was placed for several days to form a wet gel. The wet gel was dried at 100 °C for 6 h in the oven. Finally, the gel power was calcined at 400 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 2 °C/min.

Synthesis of nanocrystalline TiO_2 /(Pc) :

1.0 g of the synthesized TiO_2 power was added into the 50 mL ethanol solution. The sonication was carried out for 30 min. Then, the ethanol solution of (Pc) was added slowly into the TiO_2 suspension. The weight ratio of (Pc) to TiO_2 was 1%. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at 343 K to obtain the absorption/desorption equilibrium. Finally, precipitates were separated by centrifugation, washed several times with distilled water and dried at 373 K.

Characterization :

Diffraction patterns of samples were recorded on a Philips PNA-analytical diffractometer using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) as the X-ray source. Diffuse reflectance spectra were obtained by a Color Eye 7000-A instrument with BaSO_4 . FT-IR spectra in the range of 450–4000 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum one spectrophotometer. UV-Vis adsorption spectra of the methyl orange were recorded on Lambda EQ-OC1 spectrometer. The TEM micrograph was recorded by Zeiss-900 EM.

Evaluation of photocatalytic activity :

The photocatalytic activity of samples was evaluated in aqueous suspension by the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange (MO) solution at atmospheric pressure and room temperature. 20 ml aqueous solution of MO (10 mg/L) and 10 mg of the respective catalyst, TiO_2 /(Pc) and TiO_2 , were placed in a beaker. Walls of the beaker were covered by the aluminum foil to avoid release of the radiation. The suspension was stirred for 30 min in the dark in order to attain the equilibrium of adsorption-desorption. Then, a 500 W halogen lamp was switched on the suspension. The mixture was sampled at regular time intervals and centrifuged for 10 min at the rate of 14000 rpm. The concentration of dye in each separated sample was determined spectrophotometrically at $\lambda = 462$ nm using the Beer-Lambert equation and calibration curve of methyl orange solution (Fig. 2).

The efficiency of the photodegradation of methyl orange was calculated with the changes of its concentration

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of the methyl orange solution at $\lambda = 462$ nm.

according to the eq. (1).

$$X = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where X is the efficiency of photodegradation, C_0 (mg/L) is the initial concentration of methyl orange, C (mg/L) is the final concentration of methyl orange at time (min).

Reaction kinetics of the photocatalytic degradation followed Langmuri-Hinshelwood (L-H) kinetics model [eq. (2)] :

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_0}{C} \right) = Kt \quad (2)$$

where K is the apparent pseudo-first order reaction rate

constant (min^{-1}) and t is the reaction time (min). The slope of the plotting $\ln (C_0/C)$ versus t gives the rate constant (K).

Results and discussion

XRD analyses :

XRD patterns of TiO_2 nanoparticles and nanocrystalline $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ are shown in Fig. 3. Patterns display that the $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ and TiO_2 nanoparticles show a pure anatase phase. Peaks of the $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ (Fig. 3b) were similar to pure TiO_2 nanoparticles, which indicated the size and crystalline phase of TiO_2 have not been changed by adding the (Pc) dye¹⁷. The crystallite size of samples estimated from XRD peak broadening using Scherrer's formula (3)¹⁸.

$$t = \frac{0.9 \lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

where t is the crystallite size, λ the wavelength of X-ray radiation (Cu $K\alpha$), θ the Bragg angle and β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the most intense diffraction peak plane. It can be seen that the crystallite size of TiO_2 nanoparticles and $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ were about 25 and 21 nm, respectively. XRD patterns of $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ (Fig. 3b) do not present signals of (Pc), which could be assigned to their complete dispersion into TiO_2 with the form or low loading quantity¹⁸.

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of (a) TiO_2 nanoparticles and (b) $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$.

Thermal analysis (TG-DTA) :

TG-DTA curves of dry gel of TiO₂ nanoparticles and TiO₂/(Pc) were shown in Fig. 4. The TG curve of TiO₂ dry gel is divided into two stages (Fig. 4a). The initial weight loss (26%) occurring between 30 and 150 °C which is attributed to the evaporation of the physically absorbed water and alcohol molecules. The second weight loss (10%) between 150 and 360 °C corresponds to the combustion of organic compounds. The residual mass corresponds to TiO₂.

Likewise, it can be seen from the DTA curve that a broad endothermic reaction peak occurs in 110 °C which is associated to the evaporation of water and alcohol molecules. Exothermic peaks at around 190 and 320 °C

can be ascribed to the combustion of organic compounds. Furthermore, exothermic peaks at around 410 and 405 °C can be attributed to the anatase phase formation and anatase to rutile phase transformation, respectively.

The TG curve of TiO₂/(Pc) dry gel is divided into two stages. The initial weight loss (5%) at around 1350 °C is related to the endothermic peak in the DTA curve, which can be ascribed to the evaporation of physically absorbed water and alcohol molecules. The second weight loss (3%) for nanocrystalline TiO₂/(Pc) occurring at around 410 °C is accompanied by the exothermic peak in the DTA curve, which is attributed to the combustion of the phthalocyanine. The exothermic peak at around 780 °C corresponds to the formation of the rutile phase.

Fig. 4. TG-DTA curves of TiO₂ dry gel (a) and TiO₂/(Pc) dry gel (b).

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectra of (a) TiO₂ nanoparticles and (b) TiO₂/(Pc).

FT-IR analyses :

FT-IR spectra of TiO₂ and TiO₂/(Pc) are shown in Fig. 5. Spectrum of TiO₂/(Pc) shows the characteristic IR absorption peaks of pure (Pc) and TiO₂ nanoparticles. The bands at 728 and 855 cm⁻¹ were attributed to out-of-plane bending vibration of C-H bond of phenyl and out-of-plane bending vibration of C-H bond of porphyrines, respectively. The 1271 and 1386 cm⁻¹ bands were attributed to the C-H vibration of porphyrin and phenyl, respectively. The 1452 and 1592 cm⁻¹ bands were attributed to the C=C stretching vibration in porphyrin and phenyl, respectively.

The 1671 cm⁻¹ band was attributed to the C=N stretching vibration in porphyrin^{18,19}. The 1626 and 3437 cm⁻¹ corresponded to the bending and stretching vibrations of -OH groups on catalyst surface and surface-adsorbed water⁷. The 542 cm⁻¹ band was attributed to Ti-O stretching vibration, which shift to the higher wavelength by the introduction of (Pc) dye. The results revealed that (Pc) was synthesized successively on surface of TiO₂ nanoparticles. The results of FT-IR analysis confirmed the XRD consequences.

UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra :

UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) of TiO₂

nanoparticles and TiO₂/(Pc) are shown in Fig. 6. The reflectance spectrum of TiO₂ exhibits the characteristic absorption band at about 380 nm. This absorption is assigned to O²⁻ → Ti⁴⁺ charge transfer and electron excitation from the valance band to the conduction band²⁰. The reflectance spectrum of TiO₂/(Pc) exhibits absorption band at 600–700 nm that is corresponding to the Q band absorption spectrum of (Pc). The Q band absorption is assigned to the π → π* transition, related to π-conjugating molecules¹².

The effect of metal-free phthalocyanine on band gap energy is shown by DRS spectra. The intercept of the

Fig. 6. DRS spectra of (a) TiO₂ nanoparticles and (b) TiO₂/(Pc).

tangent to absorption will give an approximation of the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{\max}), and the band gap energy of TiO_2 could be calculated from with the following formula [eq. (4)]²¹ :

$$E_g = \frac{1240}{\lambda_{\max} \text{ (nm)}} \quad (4)$$

The band gap energy of TiO_2 nanoparticles and $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ were determined to be about 3.26 eV and 2.69 eV, respectively. Results confirmed the absorption edge of the $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ was shifted significantly into the visible region.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) :

The formation of $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ was further examined by transmission electron micrographs. TEM images (Fig. 7) of TiO_2 nanoparticles and $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ demonstrated that nanocrystalline TiO_2 impregnated with Pc and the original morphology of TiO_2 nanoparticles was still sustained. TEM micrographs showed that the particle sizes of TiO_2 nanoparticles and $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ were 22 and 18 nm, respectively which is in good agreement with the value estimated by the Scherrer's formula.

Evaluation of photocatalytic activity :

Fig. 8 shows changes of the concentration of methyl orange in the presence of TiO_2 nanoparticles and $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$

Fig. 7. TEM image of (a) TiO_2 nanoparticles and (b) $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$.

(Pc) as photocatalysts. Methyl orange solution was characterized by two main bands at about 462 nm in the vis-

Fig. 8. Changes of UV-Vis spectra of methyl orange solution with reaction time (a) $\text{TiO}_2/(\text{Pc})$ and (b) TiO_2 nanoparticles.

ible regain and 273 nm in ultraviolet regain which were attributed to the conjugated structure built by means of the azo bands and aromatic rings, respectively²².

Fig. 8a displays that in the presence of TiO₂/(Pc) the absorbance at about 462 nm and 273 nm decreased from 0.9 to 0.55 and 0.37 to 0.23, respectively. In addition, Fig. 8b shows that absorbance at about 462 nm and 273 nm decreased from 0.9 to 0.83 and 0.37 to 0.31, respectively, in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles. Results confirmed that TiO₂/(Pc) has higher photocatalytic activity than TiO₂ nanoparticles under the visible light irradiation. Also the photocatalytic activity increased as a function of the time of irradiation.

Fig. 9 demonstrates the photocatalytic degradation curves of the methyl orange with TiO₂ nanoparticles and TiO₂/(Pc) under visible light irradiation. It can be seen that TiO₂/(Pc) has higher photocatalytic activity than TiO₂ nanoparticles under the visible light. Fig. 9c showed that the efficiency of photodegradation of methyl orange in the presence of TiO₂/(Pc) catalyst was about 83% within 8 h under visible light irradiation.

Change in concentration of methyl orange in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles and without catalyst within

Fig. 9. Degradation efficiency of methyl orange (10 mg/L) aqueous solution (pH 7.0) with different catalysts (0.5 g/L) under visible light irradiation : (a) No catalyst, (b) TiO₂ nanoparticles and (c) TiO₂/(Pc).

8 h under visible light irradiation shows that the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange solution corresponds to a pseudo-first order reaction kinetics under visible light irradiation (Fig. 10).

The scheme of the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/(Pc) under visible light irradiation was demonstrated in Fig.

Fig. 10. First-order kinetics of the photocatalytic degradation methyl orange (10 mg/L) solution (pH 7.0) with different catalyst (0.5 g/L) under visible light irradiation : (a) No catalyst, (b) TiO₂ nanoparticles and (c) TiO₂/(Pc).

11. Phthalocyanine was excited by absorbing the visible light and formed an electron in the excited singlet or triplet state of (Pc) and a hole in the ground state of the (Pc). Then does the electron injection into the conduction band of TiO_2 and combines with oxygen molecules adsorbed on the surface of TiO_2 /(Pc) to form O_2^- and finally OH^\bullet . Thus the photocatalytic activity was increased by enhancing the number of active groups.

Fig. 11. The scheme of the photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 /(Pc) under visible light.

Conclusions :

In summary, the visible light photodegradation of methyl orange in aqueous suspension by using nanocrystalline TiO_2 impregnated with metal-free phthalocyanine pigment (Pc) synthesized by the chemical precipitation method at low temperature has been investigated. The preparation of titania by the sol-gel method permits the formation of anatase TiO_2 nanoparticles with a crystallite size of around 26 nm. It was found that phthalocyanine can cause a significant shift in the energy band gap to lower energies from 3.26 eV for pure TiO_2 nanoparticles to 2.69 eV for nanocrystalline TiO_2 /(Pc). This showed that the prepared TiO_2 /(Pc) is a highly efficient photocatalyst for the degradation of methyl orange under visible light. About 80% of the MO solution was degraded in the presence of TiO_2 /(Pc) after 480 min of visible light irradiation.

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